

D & Dimsum Marketing Analysis of Purchasing Decisions and Word of Mouth

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Abstract

The importance of marketing in a business, including for D&Dimsum culinary businesses, in attracting interest and purchasing decisions can be influenced by word of mouth. The purpose of this study was to determine the direct effect of product and promotion on purchasing decisions and word of mouth. The author's theoretical analysis uses a systematic literature review that is relevant to the research needs and a minimum sample size of 100 samples with an error rate of 5% with a simple random sampling technique. This study found that the percentage of research respondents' answers was dominated by answers agreeing to the product variable of 53.8%, the promotion variable of 47.2%, the purchase decision variable of 40.0% and the word-of-mouth variable of 41.4%. The research findings that local culinary products D & Dinsum from hypothesis testing that products and promotions directly have an influence on purchasing decisions and purchasing decisions directly have a relationship with the word of mouth

INTRODUCTION

The culinary business is a business that is easy for anyone to get involved in and generally the culinary business is a business that is quickly liked by anyone because almost everyone has the same taste. According to (Anggraeni et al., 2023) the culinary business ecosystem is a business system engaged in the culinary field and has a reciprocal relationship between the components in it. According to (Sutanto et al., 2021) the culinary business is a business for all time, because everyone needs to eat and drink in their lives so it is certain that the food business is always needed by everyone. The culinary business can still grow and develop along with technological developments and various artificial intelligence products. Currently, competition in the culinary business is becoming increasingly fierce and is also influenced by digitalization so that it has an impact on the knowledge, attitudes and skills needed, so that the food business can survive.

Business is closely related to purchasing decisions because consumer decisions are the main benchmark for transactions between sellers and buyers. According to (Sartien et al., 2022) industries need to pay attention to consumers and the factors that influence their purchasing decisions in efforts to market a product. This is one way to achieve the company's goals, namely by knowing what the needs and desires

of consumers or the target market are. Purchasing decisions according to (Harahap et al., 2020) is the reason how consumers determine the choice of purchasing a product according to their needs, wants and expectations so that it can cause satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the product. According to (Iskamto, 2021) that consumer decision making is an integration process that combines knowledge to evaluate two or more alternative behaviors and choose one of them.

D&Dimsum culinary business is a business that was started by one family with a product focus Dimsum which was only established in late 2022 or around 14 months has experienced rapid development, where this can be seen from the production or volume of production made has increased every day 4 kg / day can be 45 servings if it is cashed at Rp.450.000. However, from observations in the field of D&Dimsum culinary in promotion so far in the form of banners or brand billboards from culinary businesses and social media, but the increase in sales is quite good making culinary businesses loved by most residents of Silangkitang Village, South Labuhanbatu Regency. This case was first developed by (Himawan & Siwalankerto, 2014) every business must carry out the marketing function and strive for creative marketing to establish a more widely recognized business position. The marketing concept that is in accordance with the objectives is a consideration for the business to grow rapidly.

The importance of marketing in a business, including for D&Dimsum culinary businesses in attracting interest and purchasing decisions can be influenced by word of mouth, as according to (Joesyiana, 2018) the spread of word of mouth is very easy and widespread. This is what encourages researchers to evaluate how important word of mouth is in an effort to increase customer satisfaction which in turn will have an influence on the survival of the company. According to (Saad Aslam, 2011) an effective word of mouth marketing campaign connected with Influencers and Trendsetters will make consumers value word of mouth twice as much as advertising. According to him, word of mouth does have greater credibility than advertisers can imagine, let alone imagine.

Some research on word of mouth in marketing cases can influence consumer behavior, according to (Huete-Alcocer, 2017) word of mouth is one of the oldest ways to convey information and has been defined in various ways. One definition describes it as the exchange of marketing information between consumers in such a way that it plays a fundamental role in shaping their behavior and in changing attitudes towards products and services. Thus, this indicates that word of mouth is able to influence consumer behavior. Besides that, word of mouth if it can influence purchasing decisions (Tamtomo et al., 2022).

The purpose of this study focuses on whether word of mouth variables can influence purchasing decisions, including products and promos on the purchase of D&Dimsum culinary businesses. Furthermore, the novelty to be achieved from this study is that the word of mouth variable is an independent variable while consumer behavior is the dependent variable which consists of four dimensions. In running word of mouth, the seller can make anything that can encourage and facilitate consumers to talk about the products being sold, one of which is by marketing product quality, this is able to grow stories among consumers, making them happy

to help sellers market their products and invite others to experience the products being sold. (Larasati & Chasanah, 2022).

So the problem in this study is reflected in observations in the field that the increase in production and the number of consumers of the D & Dimsum culinary business has increased due to the word of mouth marketing strategy, part of the marketing communication category, which is successful so that this is the basis for the importance of proving problems regarding the implementation of *word of mouth*. Based on this, this research carries the title of Analysis of *Word Of Mouth Marketing* in Influencing Consumer Behavior and Purchasing Decisions for D & Dimsum Good Culinary Products.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Products

In marketing, products are inseparable in the economic and marketing process. Products are an important guarantee of the success or failure of a transaction process. According to (Sharma, 2020) a product can be defined as a set of utilities. This product consists of various product features and accompanying services. Customers not only buy the physical and chemical physical and chemical attributes of a product. According to (Mullins et al in Firmansyah, 2019) a product is something that can be offered to the market for attention, use, ownership, or consumption so that it can satisfy wants and needs. According to (Sustiyatik & Setiono, 2020) that products are intended to fulfill consumer desires. Indicators of poduk that support this research are attractive product design, product diversity, quality, brand and size.

Promotion

Promotion in marketing is part of the marketing mix so it deserves attention and consideration in marketing itself. The definition of promotion is the most widely defined as the process of mass communication with customers to increase sales of products or services. (Novak, 2011). According to (Odunlami & Akinruwa, 2014) promotion is one of the elements of the market mix, and a frequently used term often used in marketing. A promotional strategy includes all the ways a company uses to communicate the benefits and values of its products and persuade targeted customers to buy them. Therefore, the definition of promotion according to (Wijanarko, 2018) a communication from the seller to the buyer which aims to change the attitude and behavior of the buyer. Promotion indicators include (Muhyiddin Zainul Arifin, 2022) advertising, personal selling, sales staff and word of mouth.

Purchase Decision

Purchase decision tendencies according to (Icoz & Kutuk, 2018) through five stages, namely need recognition, information search, evaluation, purchase decisions and post-purchase behavior. According to (Pandey et al., 2021) purchasing decision is a person's attitude to buying or using a product, both goods and services, which is certain to satisfy themselves and also their willingness to bear the risks that may occur. According to (Gajjar, 2013) the term purchasing decision is defined as the

behavior displayed by consumers in searching for, buying, using, evaluating, and disposing of products and services that they expect will satisfy their needs. Indicators of purchasing decisions according to (Senggetang et al., 2019) is the stability of a product, buying habits, recommendations, repeat purchases.

Word of Mouth

After consumers make a purchase decision on a product or service, it will have an impact on other factors such as recommendations to others. Recommendations from one person to another are oral-to-oral delivery that can influence purchasing decisions and consumer satisfaction. The term word of mouth is better known as word of mouth. According to (Hameed et al., 2024) word of mouth is known as recommendation behavior; customers share their experiences with friends and family using informal communication tactics such as word of mouth to influence consumer impressions. According to (Li et al., 2024); (Liu et al., 2024) the definition of word of mouth relates to strong recommendations such as friends and family that increase trust. The indicators of word of mouth are interaction, sustainable impact, knowledge and feedback.

Based on the combination of the description of the phenomenon of the background of the problem and the literature review and the gaps in previous research, the model is modified into a framework for thinking in the research below:

Figure 1. Thinking Framework

Research Hypothesis

Based on the description of the literature review and the gaps in previous research, the hypothesis in the study is:

1. Products have a direct effect on purchasing decisions for D & Dimsum.
 2. Products have a direct effect on purchasing decisions for D & Dimsum.
- Purchasing decisions have a direct effect on D & Dimsum's word of mouth.

METHOD

This research uses research with a quantitative descriptive approach where (Putra, 2021) The research can connect the product and promotion variables with the

purchase decision and word of mouth variables. In order to sharpen the theoretical analysis, the authors use a systematic literature review that is relevant to the research needs. This study took the research subject of the D & Dinsum outlet, Lingga Tiga District, South Labuhanbatu Regency, where in determining the population and sample based on the opinion of (Hamid and Anwar, 2019). (Hamid and Anwar, 2019) that the minimum sample size is 100 samples with an error rate of 5%. The sampling method uses a simple random sampling technique, namely a sampling technique that randomly meets the researcher at the research location or when buying D & Dinsum. The data collection techniques used include observation and literature study and are supported by primary data in the form of a questionnaire containing statements related to the research. The data analysis technique in this study to fulfill the requirements and ethics of conducting validity and reliability tests and AMOS path analysis to test the hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Instrument Test Results

This research data instrument test aims to determine the extent to which the measuring instrument is able to measure what is measured (indicators of variables) through validity and reliability testing. This validity and reliability testing was carried out outside the predetermined sample of 30 people. The results of testing data instruments using the validity and reliability of this research are assisted by the SPSS application, as follows:

Table 1. Instrument Test Data Validity

Variables	Indicator	Validity Test		
		The value of r-count	Value r-tabel	Description
Products	Attractive product design	.471	0,360	Valid
	Product Diversity	.811	0,360	Valid
	Quality	.702	0,360	Valid
	Brand	.704	0,360	Valid
	Size	.467	0,360	Valid
Promotion	Advertisement	.629	0,360	Valid
	Personal selling	.697	0,360	Valid
	Sales staff	.505	0,360	Valid
	Word of mouth	.334	0,360	Valid
Purchase Decision	Stability of a product	.822	0,360	Valid
	Buying habits	.822	0,360	Valid
	Recommendation	.827	0,360	Valid
Word of Mouth	Repurchase	.789	0,360	Valid
	Interaction	.614	0,360	Valid
	Sustainable Impact	.492	0,360	Valid
	Knowledge	.397	0,360	Valid
	Feedback	.389	0,360	Valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Based on Table 1 regarding the results of the validity data instrument test, it shows that all indicators of the question variables for lifestyle variables, social environment and consumer motivation have a rcount value (Corrected Item-Total Correlation) > rtable of 0.360 so that they can be declared valid and used in research.

Table 2. Instrument Test Data Reliability

Variables	Validity Test		
	Cronbach's Alpha	Table r value	Description
Products	.822	0,60	Reliable
Promotion	.740	0,60	Reliable
Purchase Decision	.919	0,60	Reliable
Word of Mouth	.657	0,60	Reliable

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Based on Table 2 regarding the results of the reliability data instrument test, the results support the validity or consistency instrument test, also in the reliability instrument test, the lifestyle variable, social environment and consumer motivation have a rcount (Cronbach's Alpha) value > rtable of 0.600 so that it can be declared reliable and used in research.

Percentage Results of Research Variables

Quantitative data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires (instruments) to each sample and then recapitulating the percentage of answers to research variables, as follows:

Figure 2. Percentage of Answers to Research Variables

Based on the figure above regarding the percentage of answers to research variables collected, tabulated and quantified, it shows that the answers of research respondents regarding D & Dimsum Marketing Analysis of Purchasing Decisions and Word of Mouth found that respondents' answers were dominated by agreed answers for all variables, namely products, promotions, purchasing decisions and

word of mouth. Thus, the interpretation of the statement indicators in this study was interpreted quite well by the research respondents.

Goodness of Fit Index Model Test Results

Testing using the path analysis model analyzes the results by conducting suitability tests and statistical tests. The goodness-of-fit model test results are described in the table below:

Table 3. Goodness of Fit Index Test Results

Index	Criteria Value	Results	Model Evaluation
Chi-Square	Close to zero	1,652	Good
Probability Level	0,05	0,438	Good
CMIN/DF	2,00	0,826	Good
CFI	0,95	1,000	Good
RMSEA	0,08	0,000	Good
TLI	0,90	1,000	Good
GFI	0,90	0,992	Good
AGFI	0,90	0,959	Good

Source: Data Results processed, Amos 2024

Based on the Goodness of Fit Index test results above, it shows that the model used is acceptable. Because all the results of the values obtained are in accordance with the criteria so that they fall into the good criteria.

Path Analysis Hypothesis Testing Results

After the Goodness of Fit Index criteria are estimated, the next hypothesis testing path analysis is used to analyze the relationship pattern between variables with the aim of knowing the direct or indirect effect of a set of exogenous variables on endogenous related variables. (Tampi et al., 2022). The results of the path coefficient calculation using the Amos program can be seen in the figure below:

Figure 3. Calculation of Path Coefficient

Table 4. Regression Weights

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Purchase	<---	Product	.351	.093	3.787	0,000
Purchase	<---	Promotion	.446	.115	3.888	0,000
WoM	<---	Purchase	.745	.063	11.778	0,000

Source: Data Results processed, Amos 2024

Discussions

1. Products have a direct effect on purchasing decisions.

From table 4, it can be seen that in the product variable, the probability value is $(0.000) < 0.05$, so H_0 is accepted. This means that the product has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. The results of this study support research (Ruekkasaem & Sasananan, 2016) decision behavior in choosing consumer products generally prefers the type, taste and nutritional content. Dinsum product purchasing decisions made by customers pay attention to products ranging from design, diversity, quality, brand and size. (Sustiyatik & Setiono, 2020). From the analysis that supports this research that special products in the culinary business are an important thing to note, because in a culinary business such as dim sum, product quality is the most important thing for business actors to pay attention to. According to (Boros et al., 2013) local products, made with conventional procedures and with traditional flavorings, are increasingly preferred by consumers. Due to their nutritional-physiological advantages and uniqueness, these products can achieve significant competitive advantages for the national food trade. The relationship with this research is that dim sum is a form of local product in Indonesia that is liked by anyone where every consumer in making a purchase begins with information search, evaluation and post-purchase behavior.

2. Promotion has a direct effect on purchasing decisions.

From table 4, it can be seen that in the promotion variable, the probability value is $(0.000) < 0.05$, so H_0 is accepted. This means that promotion has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. The results of this study ultimately support research (Huang et al., 2022) that the promotion of local food products is one of the key components of the relationship between food, tourism, and regional development. This means that the promotion of D & Dinsum as a local culinary is able to attract the attention of local people and the community's purchasing decisions will help income and welfare. According to (Nadalipour et al., 2022) local products have great potential if the promotion mechanism leads to increased sales. This means that the promotions carried out by D & Dinsum so far, if packaged properly, will influence purchasing decisions. The factors that influence D & Dinsum's purchasing decisions include (Muhyiddin Zainul Arifin, 2022) advertising, personal selling, sales staff and word of mouth.

3. Purchasing decisions have a direct effect on word of mouth.

From table 4, it can be seen that in the purchasing decision variable, the probability value is $(0.000) < 0.05$, so H_0 is accepted. This means that purchasing decisions have a significant effect on word of mouth. The results of this study

certainly support research (Hossain et al., 2017) that the research findings recommend that word of mouth has an impact on consumer purchasing behavior. The results showed that word of mouth is built by trust and loyalty. According to (Tamtomo et al., 2022); (Ritonga et al., 2023) the results of the simple regression test show that significantly ($0.000 < 0.05$), the variable word of mouth has an effect on purchasing decisions at Jkov Koffie Jambi. From the analysis, it was found that when companies or actors do marketing by paying attention to promotions with will generate conversations among customers and the public so that D & Dinsum products consciously become news in that area and convey it to other people's ears. According to (Buana, 2021) that the indicators of word of mouth are interaction, sustainable impact, knowledge and feedback affect customer purchasing decisions.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion of this study found that the percentage of answers from research respondents was dominated by answers agreeing for the product variable of 53.8%, the promotion variable of 47.2%, the purchasing decision variable of 40.0% and the word-of-mouth variable of 41.4%. The research findings that local culinary products D & Dinsum from hypothesis testing that products and promotions directly have an influence on purchasing decisions and purchasing decisions directly have a relationship with word of mouth. So that suggestions from this study for other researchers can use a larger sample size and conduct special research development regarding the existence and existence of traditional culinary in the region as a way to maintain and preserve traditional food.

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